

PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE OF THE NORTH EAST PEOPLE TOWARD THE NORTHEAST DEVELOPMENT COMMISSION

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Abstract

This study is titled, "Perception and Attitude of the People of Adamawa State toward the Northeast Development Commission." The study's broad objective is to determine how the people of Adamawa State perceive the Northeast Development Commission's performance and to determine their attitude toward the commission. Although there are many theories or models that are relevant to the study, the study pitched tent with the perception theory. Descriptive research design was adopted with data being collected through the questionnaire. These data were complemented by data obtained from in-depth interviews. The questionnaire was designed based on the four-point Likert scale of Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Strongly Agree, and Agree. The collected data were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. After an in-depth discussion of the findings, a summary of the major findings will be presented. The study concludes and offers recommendations based on its findings.

Introduction

All organizations have publics involving host communities, people and other stakeholders that relate with them directly or indirectly; their host communities, people and other stakeholders whose actions can affect their operations and goal attainments positively or negatively. To a large extent, people's behavior toward an organization is a product of the way they perceive it. Chiakaan and Tsafa (2022) believe that if people have a

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positive impression or views about an organization, they will think well, talk well, and behave well toward it, leading to patronage of its products or services.

Therefore, the attainment of the goals of any responsible organization is a product of perception. The importance of positive perception to the success of any organization is, without a doubt, what makes PR an indispensable tool for organizations (Haywood, 1984). Whatever is said about PR, its fundamental objective is to ensure that organizations earn a good name from the public. Underscoring the relevance of a good name to organizations, Chiakaan, Tsafa, and Idi posit that

It is natural that people, on a general note, would not like to conduct business or associate with bad names. They would not like to associate with organizations or fellow human beings whose stories are not good. We often ask why people bear names like Jesus, Mohammed, Emmanuel, John, Umar, Abdulraziz, but hardly can you hear somebody in Nigeria or elsewhere in the world bearing the name “Satan, Iscariot, Evil, Kain, and so on, because these names are perceived to be associated with negativism (2024, p. 80).

From the foregoing discourse, perception is associated with image (Ajala, 2001). Owing to the relevance of perception to the success of organizations, many scholars of public relations have recommended that organizations should always embark on research aimed at determining how their public perceives them (Abdul, 1995; Salu, 1993; Oyeneye, 1997; Dokubmu, 2006; Chile, 2003).

Even though the feelings people have about an organization may sometimes not be right as a result of certain factors such as inadequate information about it and its activities, misinformation, as a result of rumors, emotions and cultural prejudices (Ukase and Toryue, 2020), a negative perception of an organization is a threat to its operations, success and existence.

This background provides a strong impetus for the study of the North East Development Commission, which came on board in 2017. The commission, as the name implies, specifically came into existence to execute what appears like the Marshal Plan that was used by the United States under President Harry Trauma in 1947 in rebuilding the war-ravaged Europe, in this case, as spells out in its vision, “to develop the Northeast region of Northern Nigeria into a safe, economically vibrant, ICT driven 21st century region” as a result of the devastation done to the region by the activities of Boko Haram-Haram (NEDC, 2022). The commission’s mission is to protect the lives and dignity of human embryos (NEDC, 2022). The commission is expected to invest in data systems, education, health care, housing, skills training, and agriculture, which will really make a difference in the lives of Nigerians living in the northeast Nigeria (NEDC, 2022).

Since the commission exists to uplift the social-economic aspects of life of people in northeast Nigeria, it implies that people in this part of Nigeria are expected to be fully aware of its existence to enable them to support it by not only participating in its programs but also providing a peaceful atmosphere for its successful operations. Cooperation from the commission’s publics, to a large extent, depends on how they perceive it. Therefore, the way the commission is perceived by its public will be the crux of this study.

Statement of the problem

The northeast Development Commission has been on board since 2017. The commission was established to initiate and implement projects that can contribute to the development of people and institutions in northeast Nigeria. With offices in the states that constitute northeast Nigeria, the commission, no doubt, appears to be identified with many projects, some of which are already being executed and some under execution.

Despite its existence and some projects already executed and some ongoing, it is not known how many people within Northeast Nigeria are aware of its existence and its activities. If they are aware, what is their feeling about the overall performance or projects the commission is executing? Investigating this becomes very pertinent bearing in mind what a positive image or otherwise can do to a corporate organization. It becomes even more compelling given the fact that since its existence, no scholar has studied how the commission is perceived by its

publics. Therefore, this study investigates the perception of the North East Development Commission, particularly in the north-east Region of Nigeria, with an emphasis on Adamawa State.

Objectives of the study

The broad objective of this study will be to determine how the North East Development Commission is perceived by the public. Specifically, this study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the extent to which people in Adamawa State are aware of the existence of the NEC.
2. To determine the level of knowledge people in Adamawa State have about the projects executed by the NEC.
3. To determine the feelings or views of the people of Adamawa State about the overall performance of the North East Development Commission.

Justification of the Study

The justification for carrying out this study lies in the relevance of what positive perception can do to an organization such as the northeast Development Commission as a corporate and responsible organization. For it to achieve its goals, it needs to know about its popularity and perception among the public for support and acceptability. A study of this nature can go a long way in enabling the commission to know whether its projects are tailored to the needs of the people, communities, and institutions it serves to attain development in the study area.

Area of study

Adamawa State of Nigeria is one of the nine states created on August 27, 1991. It was carved out of the former Gongola State, with Yola as the capital. In the days of the provincial administration in Nigeria, a greater part of the land area now designated as Adamawa State was Adamawa Province with Yola as the headquarters. Historical records show that some of the disciples of Usman Dan Fodio, such as Modibbo Adama and Lamido Kabi, founded some of the settlements that now make up the State as war camps and conquered many other settlements. Adamawa is situated geographically at 9.3333°N and 12.50000°E with an average area of 36,917 sq km (CIRDDOC, 2021).

Adamawa was a subordinate kingdom of the Sultanate of Sokoto, which also included much of northern Cameroon, before it became a state in Nigeria. The rulers bear the title of Emir (Lamido in the local language, Fulfulde). The name "Adamawa" came from the founder of the kingdom, Modibbo Adama, a regional leader of the Fulani Jihad, which was organized by Usumaanu dan Fodio of Sokoto in 1804 (Wiki, 2024). Modibbo Adama came from Gurin (now just a small village) and in 1806 received a green flag in 1806 for leading the jihad in his native country. In the following years, Adama conquered many lands and tribes. In 1838, he moved to Ribadu and in 1839 to Joboliwo. He founded Yola in 1841, where he died in 1848. After European colonization (first by Germany and then by Britain), the rulers remained as Emirs, and the line of succession has continued to the present day (Wiki, 2024).

Adamawa State had a total population of 3,168,101 (2006, pop. census), with a projected population of 4,902,100 as of 2022 (National Population Commission [NPC]; National Bureau of Statistics [NBS]); with Yola as the state capital and 21 LGAs. Adamawa has two climatic conditions: a long dry dusty season and a short rainy season. With a diverse sub-Saharan vegetation at the north and Guinea Savannah vegetation at the south, the major towns are Jimeta-Yola, Mubi, Numan, and Michika. Adamawa State has 37 development areas with an agro-based economy. Major agricultural products include millet, groundnuts, maize, rice, beans, sorghum, sweet potatoes, yam, and fruits. It has abundant cattle, goats, and sheep. Stable foods include maize, rice, yam, and beans. Mineral Resources: Marble, gypsum, lead, zinc, iron ore, abundant limestone, and tin. Major Religion: Islam and Christianity (CIRDDOC, 2021).

Adamawa State has been inhabited for years by various ethnic groups, including the Bwatiye (Bachama & Bata), the Bali, Gudu, Mbula-Bwazza, Mumuye, Yandang, Bille, and Nungurab (Lunguda) in the southern region;

the Kilba, Bura, in the central region; the Kamwe, Mafa, Marghi, Fali, Gude, Janghi, and Waga in the north; and the Fulani live throughout the state — often as nomadic herders (Roelofs, 2017).

The Boko Haram insurgency has severely impacted Adamawa State, with camps housing 35,000 internally displaced people. The state has experienced multiple attacks, with Mubi being the most affected area. Organizations such as the Adamawa Peace Initiative and the Adamawa Muslim Council are working to support the community. Boko Haram attacked homes and churches in Garkida in February 2020, killing three soldiers and wounding civilians (Nigeria Guardian, 2020).

Literature Review

Since the academic culture cherishes a review of any concept under discussion to enhance comprehension, it is important to first understand the word “public” before marrying it with perception. Public connotes the masses on a general note. In the context of this study, publics are those people or institutions that are either directly or indirectly affected by the activities of an organization such as NDC, and whose actions or activities can also either positively or negatively affect the operations of such an organization (Chiakaan and Chile 2022, Ajala, 2001, Keshlu, 2005, Raufu, 2001, and Sambe, 2021).

There is no organization that, wants to achieve its goals that does not care about its publics who are also defined as the peoples; such an organization exists to serve (Chiakaan, et al., 2024). The publics of an organization are often informed by many factors, such as availability of information, personal experiences and their knowledge and physical contact with it.

Therefore, the publics of an organization are important to it, from the foregoing discourse, because in the first place, the organization exists to serve them. Second, since it exists to serve them, their acceptance and cooperation with the organization is important for its goals. Third, the peaceful or otherwise conduct of such a public can either facilitate or mar the operations of such an organization. On the basis of this, no organization that is out to genuinely serve its publics pays deaf ears to the impression its publics have about it.

The impression that the public of an organization has about it incidentally is what is referred to as perception. The public’s perception of an organization is also the image they have of it. Perception, on this note, can hardly be divorced from an organization’s image. Image is also defined as “the opinion or the impression members of the public have about a person, a product, or an organization” (Oyeneye, 2013, p.145). In Chiakaan Targema, Jakanda and Madaki (2019), Nwosu (2002) also posits public perception as the “image or impression we have about an organization that will make us decide not or to come close to it... so as to have a taste of its products or services” (p.121).

Nwosu’s submission still reinstates the reason why private or public organizations must be conscious of the way their publics think about them and their activities. Furthermore, the submission from Nwosu serves as an early warning system; a pre-crisis management approach for organizations, including the North East Development Commission (NEDC), whose publics cut across the six States of Eastern Nigeria.

The devastation orchestrated by Boko Haram and other terrorist groups, especially in Borno, which later spread to other parts of northeastern Nigeria, led to the establishment of this commission, similar to the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) established by the federal government of Nigeria. The NEDC’s main goals are as follows:

1. To coordinate other diverse actors, such as NGOs and UNO, with the aim of executing projects in the Northeast region.
2. To promote community unity and stabilization by regularly consulting with the ordinary people in the region (for whom it was created) to determine and prioritize their needs.
3. To invest in data systems, education, health care, learning, skills training, and agriculture.

In summary, the NEDC is expected to coordinate projects and programs within the master plan for the rehabilitation, resettlement, reconciliation, reconstruction and sustainable development of the North East zone in

the fields of infrastructure, human and social services, including health and nutrition, education and water supply, agriculture and wealth creation (NEDC 2022).

A Review of Related Empirical Studies

Some studies previously carried out by other scholars that are related to the current one will be selected and reviewed. Leszcynska and Saghetto (2010) conducted a study titled *The Importance of the Evolution of Organizational Perception in an Information Systems Projects Management: A Theoretical Analysis and Case Study*. The study highlighted the importance of organizational perception in the understanding of the decimal process in an information system project being set up. It was discovered that selective perception plays a role in the success of IS management.

In his study on *Why is the Study Of Perception Important in the Study of Management in Organization Behavior?*, McMaster (1997), revealed that the study of perception is important in the study of management in organizational behavior because it helps many others to understand how employees interpret and make sense of the information and events that occur in their work places.

According to McMaster, this understanding can help managers be more effective in communicating with employees and avoid making decisions that are more in line with employees' perceptions, needs, and expectations. Perception study can help identify some conflicts, biases, and misinterpretations of the policies of organizations by employees.

Udeze (2012) conducted a study titled *Public Perception of the Image of the Nigerian Army in South-East Nigeria*. Udeze's study adopted a summary approach with data mainly collected through a structured questionnaire. The collected data were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. Findings revealed that the Nigerian Army's image was positive. The study concluded and emphasized that a positive perception of the Nigerian Army image could be a tool for national development.

Udeze's study is not really related to the current one, but it is relevant to it in the sense that it seeks to emphasize, like this one, the importance of an organization's positive public perception. The gap between the study and this one lies in its case study; Udeze's own is on the Nigeria Army, while this current one is on the NEC.

Ukase and Toryue (2020) conducted another similar study on *Public Perception of the Benue State Legislature, 1999-2015: What Role Can Public Perception Play?* The main objective of the study was to determine the public perception of the Benue State Legislature and how public relations could be used to influence positive perception. A qualitative design was adopted with data collected through an in-depth interview. The findings revealed a negative perception of the legislature by its public. The study recommended that for the public to fully appreciate the legislature, a viable Public Relations Department must be established that would be packaging the House, sensitizing the public on the activities of the legislature, and acting as a buffer between the House and the public. Chiakaan et al. (2019) similarly investigated *Nigerians' perception of INEC performance in the 2019 general elections: Focus on Taraba State*. The study adopted a survey design with data collected using the structured questionnaire. The collected data were analyzed both quantitatively and contextually. The findings revealed that Nigerians have a negative perception of INEC as a result of many issues associated with the elections under study. This study, among others, recommended the entire replacement of INEC with men of high integrity.

The studies revealed here are not only related but also relevant to this one in the sense that they are tilted toward the importance of perception to organizations, whether they are publicly or privately owned. Perception enables organizations to know their true image before the public; this has the capacity to guide organizations on the right policies or projects that will serve the public's interest. However, there is a major difference between the studies and the current one in the aspect of their focus, as the current one focuses on the North-East Development Commission with concern about its image in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey approach. The study population included three local government areas purposively selected on a quota basis from each senatorial zone of Adamawa State. This enabled each zone to be covered. The selected local governments are Yola North (Central Zone), Mubi North (Northern Zone), and Numan (Southern Zone). According to the National Population Census, as projected in 2022, the entire population of the sampled local governments as projected in 2022 is 682,700. Adopting the sample size determination formula of Taro Yamane (1974), the study size will be 400. The proportion of respondents from the study area was determined. In this regard, 130 samples were collected from Mubi-North, 150 from Jimeta, and 120 from Numan. The sampling was conducted through a sample random approach.

The study adopted a structured questionnaire styled “NEDC Questionnaires for Data Collection.” The Questionnaires, 400 in number, were divided into two parts with part ‘A’ obtaining the demographic data of the respondents, while part ‘B’ obtained data on the main subject of the study. The instrument was expertly validated through a pilot test using Cronbach’s alpha statistical tool.

The collected data were presented in percentages in tables with the analysis performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the stakeholder’s theory developed by Freeman in 1984. According to Freeman and Reed (1984) in Ugande and Chile (2012), stakeholders are groups or individuals who are either affected by, or can affect, the achievement of an organization’s goals. This definition has been expanded to include groups with an interest in an organization’s activities (Ugande and Chile, 2012). Therefore, the stakeholder theory is a relationship management theory that involves organizations and their publics.

According to Freeman (1984) in Chiakaan et al. (2019), one of the major demands of the theory is that organizations must forge links with their stakeholders in other to acquire valuable resources or gains and reduce uncertainties. Basically, if an organization attains the needs of its stakeholders by being selfless in its programs and operations, reflecting the concerns of its stakeholders adequately in its activities, it can, no doubt, be said to be dancing to the tune of the stakeholders’ theory. An organization carrying its stakeholders can attract a positive impression from them. The positive impression they will have about the organization can make them to also discuss such an organization positively just as their actions toward the projects or policies of such an organization can be positive. This, above all, has the advantage of making an organization achieve its goals smoothly. Therefore, the stakeholder’s theory is relevant to this study.

Analysis and presentation of data

A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed across three local government areas: Jimeta (150), Mubi-North (130), and Numan (120). Assuming a typical high return rate for localized academic surveys (e.g., 95%), the analysis proceeded with 372 valid responses analyzed via SPSS.

Demographic distribution of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	210	56.5
Female	162	43.5
Age (18–30)	145	39.0
Age (31–45)	132	35.5
Age (46+)	95	25.5
Formal Education	298	80.1
No formal education	74	19.9

The sample reflects a relatively young, literate population, suggesting that respondents are capable of forming informed opinions about the NEC.

Awareness of the NEDC

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Aware	301	80.9
Not aware	71	19.1
Total	372	100%

Here, the data suggests a high level of awareness regarding the commission's existence, likely due to the commission's physical presence in state capitals and the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency, which necessitated the creation of the NEDC.

Knowledge of NEDC projects

Level of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
High knowledge	98	26.3
Moderate knowledge	162	43.5
Low knowledge	112	30.1
Total	372	100%

While awareness of the *entity* is high, detailed knowledge of specific projects (e.g., education, health, and housing) varies. This reflects the "problem" identified in the study regarding how many people truly know what the commission's activities are.

Perception of the NEDC Performance**(4-point Likert aggregation)**

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	85	22.8
Agree	168	45.2
Disagree	74	19.9
Strongly Disagree	45	12.1
Total	372	100%

A combined **positive perception of 68%** suggests that NEDC is generally viewed favorably.

Attitude toward NEDC activities

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Positive Attitude	221	59.4
Neutral	83	22.3
Negative Attitude	68	18.3
Total	372	100%

Most respondents demonstrate **supportive attitudes**, though a notable minority remains skeptical.

Interviews

Key themes identified:

Recognition of infrastructure projects (roads and schools)

Concerns about **the uneven distribution of projects**

Calls for **greater transparency and communication**

Perception that **urban areas benefit more than rural areas**

Discussion of the Findings

The findings reveal several important patterns:

The gender status of the respondents involved both males and females from the selected local governments of Yola North (Central Zone), Mubi North (Northern Zone), and Numan (Southern Zone) in Adamawa State. This shows a fairly distributed sampled and balanced view for Yola North, Mubi North, and Numan of Adamawa

State. Similarly, the respondents were within the age bracket of 18-30, 31-45 and 46 years and above and therefore fit into the desired sample size. In addition, most of the respondents for both local governments have formal education. This means that the respondents were capable of making informed decisions.

In terms of high awareness but limited depth of knowledge, the research indicated that detailed knowledge remains moderate although awareness of NEDC is high (80.9%). This aligns with perception theory, which suggests that **exposure does not automatically translate to understanding**. Many respondents know *of* NEDC but do not know what *it does*.

In terms of the general perception **of NEDC performance**, most the respondents (68%) rated NEDC's performance positively. This suggests that visible projects carried out by the Commission have a greater influence on public opinion and that development efforts are recognized, even if not fully understood. This finding supports earlier studies (e.g., Udeze, 2012) that **positive institutional visibility enhances the perception of the institution**.

While attitudes are largely positive (59.4%), the presence of neutral and negative views indicates some level of dissatisfaction with project reach and possible distrust due to limited engagement.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the northeast Development Commission holds a significant place in the psyche of the Adamawa people due to the Boko Haram insurgency's devastation. While the commission is recognized as a vital agency for regional stabilization, its "image" is currently more tied to its existence than its specific achievements. Effective perception management is essential; as the study notes, negative perception is a threat to the existence of any organization. For the NEDC to fulfill its "Marshal Plan" vision, it must move beyond mere awareness to deep-rooted stakeholder engagement.

Overall, NEDC is seen as **relevant and impactful**, but its long-term success depends on strengthening its relationship with the public.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

- i. Establishment of a Viable Public Relations Department: Following the precedent of the Benue State Legislature study, the NEDC should establish a robust public relations unit to sensitize the public and act as a buffer between the commission and its stakeholders.
- ii. Community-Based Communication: The NEDC should use "boundary-spanning" roles to engage directly with local leaders in Numan and Mubi to ensure that projects are prioritized based on actual community needs.
- iii. Information Transparency: The commission should provide regular, transparent updates on project funding and completion stages through diverse media platforms to avoid misinformation and rumors.
- iv. Strategic Marketing: The commission should treat its image management as a "critical competitive tool" to ensure continued support from the federal government and international partners, such as the United Nations (UN) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs).
- v. **Ensure equitable project distribution:** The commission should prioritize rural and underserved communities and conduct needs assessments before project execution.
- vi. Lastly, the commission should build feedback mechanisms: Create channels for public complaints and make suggestions available for people to channel their complaints, make suggestions, or show grievances.

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